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Review of the Relationship between Food Insecurity (Nutrients Imbalance) and Non-Communicable Diseases (NCDs)

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Abstract

The Glob today is facing an “epidemic” of diet-related non-communicable diseases (DR-NCDs), along with widely prevalent under-nutrition resulting in substantial socioeconomic burden. The aim of this paper is to review the relationship between nutrients and energy metabolism and implications for non-communicable diseases (NCDs) in different parts of the world’s so as to understand optimal choices for healthy diets for the prevention of NCDs. The literature search was carried out in PubMed and Google Scholar search up to December 2019. A manual search for all other references, national and medical databases was also carried out. A decreasing intake of coarse cereals, pulses, fruits and vegetables, an increasing intake of meat products and salt, coupled with declining levels of physical activity due to rapid urbanization have resulted in escalating levels of obesity, atherogenic dyslipidemia, subclinical inflammation, metabolic syndrome, type 2 diabetes mellitus, and coronary heart disease in different parts of the world. Studies also suggest that adverse perinatal events due to maternal nutritional deprivation may cause low-birth weight infants, which, coupled with early childhood “catch-up growth”, leads to obesity in early childhood, thus predisposing to NCDs later in life. In view of rapidly increasingly imbalanced diets, a multisectoral preventive approach is needed to provide balanced diets to pregnant women, children and adults, and to maintain a normal body weight from childhood onwards, to prevent the escalation of DR-NCDs.

Keywords: obesity, overweight, diabetes, coronary heart disease, diet, energy metabolism, metabolic syndrome

1. Introduction

1.1. Background

Basic nutrients, such as carbohydrates, fats, and proteins, are the foundation of all life activities. They constitute the carbon skeleton (intermediate metabolites) of various functional molecules, and provide energy through oxidative decomposition. Traditionally, the main aim of nutrition is prevent and treat nutritional deficiencies. However, when nutrition is adequate or excessive, the body faces the problems of quantitative control of the nutrients absorption and storage. Over nutrition, especially absorption and storage of energy, can not only affect health but also cause many diseases such as diabetes, cardiovascular diseases, obesity, hypertension, and hyperlipidemia. Further, over nutrition reduces reproductive capacity and promotes the development of various cancers that will seriously affect quality of life, survival, and reproduction in human beings.

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Because of over-nutrition, nutriology based on nutritional requirements cannot make recommendations for nutrient intake in daily life because nutrient absorption, energy storage, and oxidative energy supply control vary from person to person.

Even during evolution, nutritional experience seems to be recorded in the nucleosomes and DNA, which involves all aspects of nutrient sensing, cell communication, metabolic regulation, gene expression, and epigenetic modifications. However, food intake is a fundamental activity of the human body and is a source of energy. This study reviews the relationship among energy absorption, metabolism, and human health to systematically analyze and discuss signaling processes, metabolic control mechanisms, and corresponding diseases due to over nutrition.

The global health threat posed by non-communicable diseases (NCDs) is enormous. NCDs are responsible for 63% of 57 million deaths worldwide and they are disproportionately high in lower and middle income countries (LMIC) and populations. In 2008, nearly 80% of NCD deaths – 29 million- occurred in LMIC, with 29% of deaths occurring below the age of sixty while in high income countries only 13% of the NCD deaths are premature. Total NCD deaths are projected to rise to 52 million by 2030; furthermore, NCDs are projected to cause almost three quarters as many deaths as communicable, maternal, perinatal and nutritional diseases by 2020 and to exceed them as the most common causes of death by 2030 (45)

The World Economic Forum has placed NCDs among the most important and severe threats to economic development. A study by the Institute of Medicine in 2010 found that NCDs cost developing countries between 0.02% and 6.77% of their GDP, a greater burden than that caused by malaria in the 1960s or AIDS in the 1990s. NCDs have a negative impact on poverty and hunger as they lead to reductions in productivity and family income. Their impact on national economies translates into fewer jobs and fewer people escaping poverty, perpetuating the vicious cycle of malnutrition and poor health outcomes (41).

According to different studies shows that nutrition and NCDs needs more attention in the fact that NCDs and nutrition are closely linked; underweight, overweight and obesity, are having a direct impact on the global rise in NCDs. While under-nutrition kills in early life, it can also lead to increased risk of NCDs and death later in life Under-nutrition still affects over 1 billion people worldwide and 36 countries are considered high burden.

Hence, risk factors for the appearance of non-communicable diseases have emerged. The aim of this term paper is (1) to overview the relationship between nutrients intake balance and metabolic disturbance or non-communicable diseases and (2) to review the cause of metabolic disturbance, effect of metabolic disturbance and regulatory mechanism.

A systematic literature search was conducted and the reviewed paper on the metabolic disturbance and food intake. Databases searched were done on PubMed and Food Science and Technology Abstracts. Titles, abstracts and keywords were searched from internet and inception up to December 2019. Search terms included comprehensive terms and synonyms for the causes and intervention of metabolic disturbance was reviewed regarding:

- the prevalence and/or trends of NR-NCDs, including obesity, hypertension/high blood pressure, type 2 diabetes, any cardiovascular or heart disease, stroke, high cholesterol, triglycerides, non-alcohol steato-hepatitis/fatty liver, metabolic syndrome for aged children, adolescents or adults.

2) Energy storage and oxidation

Energy absorption should obey the law of energy conservation. Although different people have different absorption rates, energy absorbed by the body should meet the following formula:

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$\Delta E_{in} = \Delta E_s + \Delta E_c$ Where E_{in} is the calorie of total absorbed energy, E_s is the calorie of stored energy, and E_c is the calorie of consumed energy.

Fats, carbohydrates, and proteins are called energy substances. Proteins serve as carbon and nitrogen sources. Because energy metabolism is essentially a moderate burning process in which CO₂ is generated via decarboxylation under constant temperature and pressure, energy production depends on dehydrogenation and electron transfer to oxygen through oxidation–respiration chain that finally results in the release of water. This process is coupled with ATP synthase complex and promotes phosphorylation of ADP to ATP. Proteins are not optimal energy material because their oxidation results in the formation of nitrogenous compounds whose accumulation can lead to toxicity.

Different studies show that when energy absorption exceeds its consumption, surplus energy is stored for energy shortage in the future. It is clear that carbohydrates are usually stored in the form of muscle and liver glycogen to supply energy for muscle movement and various physiological activities, especially during stress. However, this storage form cannot change with energy absorption and is not the major mechanism for long-term energy storage. Long-term energy storage only involves conversion of glucose into fat, and this fat is majorly stored subcutaneously, especially under the belly. This storage method is of vital significance for biological adaptation, which not only provides energy to the body in the cold season when food shortage occurs but also effectively prevents heat loss. This storage method provides hibernating animal's adequate supply of energy for the recovery in the subsequent year. However, in advanced animals, such humans, this storage method has a key problem, in that carbohydrates are converted to acetyl coenzyme A (acetyl-CoA) through the central metabolic pathways, thus resulting in the synthesis of fatty acids that are stored in the form of fat. However, the process is irreversible in human beings and other advanced animals except plants and microorganisms, in which undergo gluconeogenesis to form glucose and other carbon sources via glycosylate. In other words, the energy stored in human beings in the form of fat can only be decomposed through energy consumption and circulated in the form of ketone bodies. The major component of ketone bodies is β -hydroxybutyrate (β -OHB), which is an energy molecule from fat and is circulated in animals in vivo. This is mainly observed during long-term exercising or fasting. When the body is in a state of starvation, glycogen is the first choice for producing energy, followed by adipose cells or tissues. Fat is mobilized and transported to the liver where they are converted into ketone bodies, which are again transported to the site of energy requirement via the circulatory system and mitochondrial oxidation.

Therefore, in addition to a certain function of reservation, accumulation of fat itself is the signal of energy accumulation. In human beings and higher animals, ketone body metabolism is the only way to reduce fat accumulation. Several studies have shown that ketone body metabolism and ketogenic diets play an important role in many diseases caused by metabolic homeostasis and imbalance [55].

2.1) Energy absorption and metabolic homeostasis

The association between energy intake and balanced metabolism and health has been the subject of numerous researches due to the rise in disorders brought on by over-nutrition. Following the ingestion of energy-producing substances like glucose, the body initially triggers insulin secretion, then suppresses glucagon activity and gluconeogenesis, and lastly encourages glycogenesis. The situation is inverted in an emergency, meaning that the body first causes insulin resistance and activates glucagon to make sure that energy consumption and storage are tightly regulated to maintain metabolic balance. Once the metabolic equilibrium is out of balance, diseases develop.

2.2) Control of synthesis and catabolism

Control of synthesis and catabolism Hormone receptors, including PPARs and liver X receptor (LXR), and transcription factors interact and respond to nutrient signals in vivo. Crosstalk between thyroid hormones and

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fat nutrients may involve multiple components such as retinoid X receptor (RXR) heterodimer partners, DNA-binding sites, and cofactors of transcription factors. TR, PPAR – α , PPAR- γ , and LXRs activate nuclear receptors having similar structure and activation mode and undergo hetero-dimerization with RXR [56]. They have highly conserved DNA-binding domain and zinc finger domain to identify DNA response element. Ligand binding domain determines specific ligands for each receptor and contains the (a contact) domain to interact with other receptors, co-activators, and co-repressors. Recent studies have found that d-glucose and D-glucose phosphate can be directly used as agonists of LXR α and LXR γ , suggesting that LXRs may coordinate the metabolism of glucose and fatty acids [57]. These findings provide additional evidence that glucose and fat metabolism are regulated during metabolic homeostasis by TR/T3 and LXR/agonists (glucose and cholesterol) [58] and confirm that coordination of fatty acids and glucose between energy storage and consumption is necessary for maintaining metabolic balance. Limitation of calories in cells or organisms can effectively prolong their lifespan and delay aging. Cyclic AMP response element-binding protein (CREB), a transcription factor with helix–loop–helix and leucine zipper domains, is expressed and activated during long-term starvation [59]. At the beginning of starvation, pancreatic β -cells release glucagon to maintain glucose level in the plasma. When insulin reaches hepatocytes, glucagon binds to the corresponding GPCRs and switches GDP/GTP to continuously stimulate adjacent membrane-bound adenylate cyclase to convert ATP into cAMP. Intracellular increase in cAMP stimulates protein kinase A (PKA) to catalyze and regulate the dissociation of subunits [60]. However, CREB alone cannot play this role by activating the transcription of its target genes. It combines with CREB-regulated transcription co-activator (CRTC2/TORC2). A previous study has confirmed that CRTC2/TORC2 is the key regulator of glucose homeostasis during starvation [61]. During fasting, CRTC2/TORC2 is present in the nucleus and binds to phosphorylated CREB to enhance the transcription of gluconeogenic genes. Under the action of cAMP and CRTC2/TORC2 for 6 h, liver cells are acylated by histone acetyltransferase p300 to regain the ubiquitination capability. However, when cAMP level is low, another co-activator—NAD-dependent deacetylase1 (SIRT1)—promotes the deacetylation of CRTC2/TORC2 to promote the degradation of target proteins [62]. During starvation, increased glucocorticoid concentration promotes the expression of gluconeogenic genes through the binding of GR to the promoter region of GRE. GR-mediated transcription also requires various hepatocyte nuclear factors (HNFs) to promote the transcription of gluconeogenic genes for maximum activity.

High levels of insulin may decrease the abundance and activity of SIRT1, thus promoting a decrease in the transcription of PGC-1 α . These studies enable us to understand various hormones such as insulin, glucagon, glucocorticoids, and leptin that control gluconeogenesis. Insulin and glucagon control FoxO, CREB, CRTC2/TORC2, and PGC-1 and acetylation/deacetylation, thus controlling the expression of gluconeogenic genes during starvation and food intake via synergistic modulation in the presence of C/EBPs and HNFs. Glucose catabolism does not depend on diet or fasting. To ensure maintenance of catabolism and life activities under starvation, the body stimulates gluconeogenesis in cells to supplement blood glucose by controlling glycogenolysis. During food intake, the body activates the synthesis of insulin and promotes glucokinase to synthesize liver and muscle glycogen by using glucose, thus maintaining stable levels of blood glucose.

2.3) Respiration and oxidative phosphorylation

According to research on the physiology of exercise, the blood's lactic acid content rises quickly during the early stages of activity and then stabilizes after reaching a threshold known as the maximal lactate steady state (MLSS). MLSS is a significant indicator of fitness, health, age, and sports strength training [63–65]. From a metabolic standpoint, following multistep dehydrogenation, glucose uses oxidative respiration to make water by transferring electrons to oxygen, which in turn triggers oxidative phosphorylation, which generates and releases ATP. The only practical means of preserving the body's redox balance and neutral physiological pH is through this crucial mechanism. Lactic acid also moves between tissues, organs, organelles, and cells [66]. The primary mechanism of respiration and oxidative phosphorylation is the acetyl-CoA generated by the oxidation of fatty acids and carbohydrates. Moving lactate across cells can help balance the oxidative phosphorylation and oxygen

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supply when oxidative phosphorylation's capacity is limited. Two factors limit respiration and oxidative phosphorylation: first, the mitochondria's capacity for oxidative phosphorylation is limited, and second, the synthetic metabolism, which uses the TCA cycle to supply carbon sources for a number of essential amino acids, including oxaloacetate and α -ketoglutarate, is limited. While the latter happens during cell proliferation and tumor growth, the former happens during high-intensity exercise and regular physical activity [67]. An important indicator of oxidative phosphorylation, blood lactic acid circulation has significant research and application value in athlete training, adaptation to high altitude hypoxia environments, and the assessment of the diagnosis, management, and effectiveness of diseases like metabolic syndrome, diabetes, and cancers.

3) Over-nutrition and metabolic syndrome

Over-nutrition is a major cause of modern lifestyle diseases. Studies on energy absorption and consumption indicate that appropriate storage of surplus energy is necessary to extend the lifespan of animals and humans. However, the contents of muscle and hepatic glycogen cannot go up with the increase of energy substance (calorie). Therefore, surplus energy substances such as fats, carbohydrates, or proteins are usually stored in adipose tissues. Removal of excess fat is essential for better survival. The most important system in advanced animals is the immune defense system. A reasonable assumption is that nutrients absorbed by the body must ensure the operation of the immune defense system, indicating that immune deficiency does not occur unless there is nutrition deficiency (or pathogen invasion such as HIV or congenital genetic diseases). Over-nutrition often results in strong immune responses such as allergy and various inflammatory diseases. Other ways to eliminate the over-accumulated energy include improve glucagon secretion, reduce insulin secretion, and induce insulin resistance to inhibit glycogenesis. Excessively accumulated energy can be excreted as urine glucose and by gluconeogenesis. Another method to eliminate the excessively accumulated energy is through cell proliferation. Apparently, unlimited proliferation of various cancer cells can meet this requirement. To avoid the disease, proper physical activity is very essential to burn the accumulated energy.

3.1) Diabetes and insulin

The number of diabetic patients worldwide is too high. According to a 2011 statistics, approximately 90 million patients have diabetes. Generally, people in richer countries often consume diets containing more carbohydrates and fat and perform less physical activity or exercise, which in turn increases the prevalence of diabetes. In high-income countries, diabetic patients account for nearly 8% of the adult population while in middle-income countries, they account for >10% of the adult population. Higher incidence of diabetes in these countries is mainly because of more people aged below 50 years develop diabetes compared with those in developed countries, indicating a direct correlation between diabetes and a change in lifestyle in these countries [90]. As mentioned above, when absorbed or accumulated energy is too high, mechanisms to increase energy consumption must be initiated by the body. A direct metabolic pathway to consume surplus energy is to increase the consumption of blood and urine glucose. Insulin promotes the synthesis of glycogen and decrease glycogenolysis in the blood or urine. The insulin resistance, as well as the reduction of insulin secretion and activity can increase the carbohydrate consumption. Diabetes can be prevented by inhibiting excessive nutrient accumulation before the body receives a signal to improve energy consumption. Moreover, physical activity and exercise are important to delay or prevent obesity and diabetes [91]. Cancer and Warburg effect although cancers seem to have no obvious correlation with obesity and excessive nutrition, they can eliminate excessive accumulated nutrients. The unlimited proliferation of cancer cells consume large amount of glucose to provide energy for cell proliferation, and obtain the proteins, carbohydrates and other essential substances originated from the carbon source through central metabolic pathways. Warburg effect is the key way for cancer cells firing a plurality of synthetic and metabolic pathways based on various carbon skeletons [67]. Once glucose is converted to pyruvate via glycolysis, the pyruvate is converted to acetyl-coA by the dehydrogenase system. Moreover, like fatty acid oxidation, dehydrogenation and decarboxylation involved in TCA cycle provide energy for cells [92]. However, this is not observed in cancer cells because TCA cycle is the basic pathway in

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cancer cells to synthesize glutamic acid, aspartic acid, and other important raw materials. Cancer cells can only provide raw materials as carbon source by consuming large amounts of glucose. Moreover, cancer cells derive large amount of energy via lactic acid fermentation [93], which is the well-known Warburg effect. Both cancer and diabetes are dependent on glucose; therefore, diabetes and cancer often share many characteristics, treatment methods, targets, and pathways [94].

3.2) Obesity and inflammation

Excessive energy buildup is the cause of obesity. When energy molecules like fats and carbs are absorbed more than they are consumed, fat builds up. The development of obesity is significantly influenced by energy molecules, particularly fat [95]. Numerous studies have demonstrated that the emergence of inflammatory disorders frequently coexists with obesity. Nonalcoholic fatty liver disease, for instance, affects 75–100% of obese persons; chronic nonalcoholic steatohepatitis, liver cirrhosis, portal hypertension, hepatocellular carcinoma, and other conditions affect 20% of obese people [96–98]. Jorge et al. confirmed that obesity-induced inflammation depends on the activation of Toll-like receptors 4 and 9 (TLR4 and TLR9, respectively) using animals lacking an inflammasome and mice that were overweight. These methodical studies have demonstrated that the metabolic rhythm is determined by the intricate sensing and interaction between NLRs and TLRs. Accordingly, inflammasomes may be triggered by intestinal sensing disorders. Furthermore, the inflammatory response is significantly influenced by the liver's excessive fat buildup [99]. Therefore, in order to eliminate excessive fat accumulation, inflammatory cytokines must be activated. This, in turn, activates the metabolism of fatty acids. After being produced in the liver, the ketone bodies are discharged into the bloodstream and carried to other organs or tissues for additional supersession, which typically results in inflammation (like hepatitis). The law of energy conservation, after all, cannot be violated by the body.

3.3 Overweight, obesity and cardiovascular diseases

According to the World Health Organization (WHO) estimates, chronic diseases will account for approximately three-quarters of all the deaths in the developing world by the year 2020. In this regard, the increasing incidence of overweight and obesity could be an emerging public health problem in the low and middle income countries. As a result, new cases of the metabolic syndrome may appear which is likely to create enormous socio-economic and public health burdens for poorer nations in the near future. In countries undergoing epidemiological transition, a complex picture relating to increased food consumption and concomitant changes towards sedentary lifestyles is frequently found. The effects of these changes are particularly severe in the non-European populations with a 'thrifty genotype' and those with an inherited metabolic predisposition to adverse body fat-patterning, i.e. abdominal obesity.

The past few decades have seen a sharp rise in the incidence of obesity. One of the major public health concerns in the United States and other Westernized nations, obesity is linked to several negative health consequences and significant financial expenses (Kuczmarski et al. 1994, Pi-Sunyer 1993). As a result, research has concentrated on determining the main causes of obesity in order to find practical methods that would effectively stop more weight gain and possibly even cause weight loss.

One of the numerous subfields of obesity research has concentrated on the potential effects of dietary composition on energy balance and food intake regulation. Dietary fiber's impact on energy intake regulation has received less attention than the roles of dietary fat, protein, and carbohydrates, which have all been the subject of several research (Barkeling et al. 1990, Burton-Freeman et al. 1997 and 1998, Foltin et al. 1992, Hill and Blundell 1986, Rolls 1995a). This essay aims to address the significance of dietary fiber in relation to human energy control.

Obesity is becoming more widespread at younger ages. Numerous studies have connected childhood obesity to later morbidity and mortality in adulthood [Nieto et al. 1992; DiPietro et al. 1994; Must et al. 1992; Olshansky et al. 2005], and childhood obesity frequently continues into adulthood [Serdula et al. 1993; Guo et al. 2002;

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Troiano et al. 1995; Whitaker et al. 1997]. 20.6% of children aged 2 to 5 in the United States were overweight, according to NHANES IV [Ogden et al. 2002] (BMI 85th percentile of the gender and age specific growth charts). This frequency was much greater in older children, with 30.4% of adolescents (12–19 years old) and 30.3% of children aged 6–11 being overweight. Among children ages 0–23 months, 2–5 years, 6–11 years, and teenagers, the prevalence of obesity (BMI 95th percentile) was 11.4%, 10.4%, 15.3%, and 15.5%, respectively. All ethnicities and genders are impacted by childhood obesity, although minorities are disproportionately affected. Life expectancy is significantly reduced by obesity, particularly in younger people and those who are extremely obese (BMI > 45). Males and African-Americans (AA) are more negatively impacted, with a 5–20 year lower life expectancy among those aged 20–30 [Fontaine et al. 2003].

It is well known that young people who are obese often have cardiometabolic risk factors, and these risk factors often cluster. Using factor analysis, Goodman et al. [2005] discovered four clusters of risk factors in teenagers and concluded that the most significant impact on cumulative cardiometabolic risk was obesity. This grouping of risk factors, referred to as the metabolic syndrome or cardiometabolic syndrome (CMS), is thought to be caused by obesity, insulin resistance, and subclinical inflammation. We have decided to use the term cardiometabolic syndrome in this review. central fat, An ecological analysis of how the consumption of meat, which provides excess calories in the modern diet, contributes to the incidence of obesity.

Due to the Middle East's highest dietary energy surplus among developing nations, significant changes in dietary and physical activity patterns, as well as a sharp increase in risk factors for chronic diseases, particularly obesity, are observed in tandem with the region's rapidly changing demographics¹⁰. Due to nutritional imbalance, the Middle East has one of the highest prevalence rates of obesity globally, according to the International Obesity Task Force. Urbanization is rapidly accelerating in emerging nations, which could have an effect on obesity and its aftereffects in the future, making this a significant matter. According to certain research, being physically inactive is linked to being overweight (22, 28, 31). Leisure time, transportation, job hours, and domestic chores are just a few of the many components that make up the complex behavior of physical exercise. Our results also demonstrated the extremely low levels of physical activity in the general population, with obese people engaging in significantly fewer of all three categories of activities than non-obese people.

3.4 Cardiovascular Disease

Since the mid-1960s, mortality rates from coronary heart disease have also significantly declined, as have age-standardized death rates from stroke since the 1940s. Improvements in heart attack and stroke therapies, secondary prevention (early diagnosis and treatment of high blood pressure and high blood cholesterol), and primary prevention (e.g., decreases in the prevalence of tobacco smoking and saturated fat intake) are all responsible for this success. However, despite a 17% decrease in the death rate from cardiovascular disease during the final decade of the 20th century, the number of deaths rose by 2.5% year due to the population's expansion beyond the age of 65.

3.5 Cancer

Between 1991 and 2000—the most recent year for which data are available in the United States—the age-standardized death rate from all malignancies combined fell by 7.2%. Both cigarette smoking decreases and advancements in early identification and treatment are responsible for the overall decline in the cancer mortality rate. Similar to cardiovascular disease, the number of persons who develop or pass away from cancer each year keeps rising due to population expansion and aging, even though the age-standardized death rate from the condition has decreased. Over the course of nine years, from 1991 to 2000, the annual number of deaths from all cancers combined grew by 7.4%, or over 38,400 deaths. However, since the United States' population grew by almost 10% (24 million) during that time, with an even greater percentage increase in the number of people

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65 and older, this increase was less than what would have happened if the age-specific or age-adjusted death rates had not been declining.

3.6 Diabetes

From 1990 to 2001, the prevalence of diabetes increased by 61%, with about 1.3 million Americans developing diabetes each year. This overall increase in diabetes prevalence reflects an increase in type 2 diabetes (which accounts for 90% to 95% of all diagnosed cases) due to the epidemic increase in excess body weight occurring in the US population during that period.²⁶ According to current trends in childhood and adult obesity, the prevalence of type 2 diabetes and its complications will continue to increase.

3.7 Nutritional imbalance during development can increase risk for disease later in life

Poor or imbalanced maternal diet, improper body composition, high physical workload prior to and during pregnancy, and poor fetal supply line function (e.g., placental malfunction) are the main causes of fetal undernutrition globally. In low- and middle-income nations, maternal undernutrition is still a significant issue. In addition to individuals who experience food insecurity, women with low incomes and educational attainment are more likely to consume inadequate and subpar diets. Although maternal diet has been primarily implicated in the present evidence of fetal influences on later health, new research indicates that maternal obesity, excessive weight gain during pregnancy, and gestational diabetes play a significant role in influencing the risk of disease in the offspring.

The impact of maternal starvation on children is demonstrated by a historical cohort of Dutch people whose mothers experienced the 1944–1945 wartime famine. Compared to children of women who were pregnant before or after the famine, children of women exposed during the early stages of pregnancy had a higher chance of developing the metabolic syndrome as adults. The consequences varied according to the gestational trimester during which famine occurred. Nearly 60 years later, epigenetic examinations of these individuals reveal differential methylation in a number of growth and metabolic regulation genes that depend on sex and exposure period during pregnancy. Although the effect is slight, those exposed during the peri-conceptual phase have also been found to have hypomethylation at the promoter of IGF2, a maternally imprinted gene important in growth and development, in comparison to their unexposed siblings. According to other, more recent cohorts, people who were exposed to the 1968–1970 Nigerian civil war famine during pregnancy and infancy were more likely to develop hypertension, poor glucose tolerance, and overweight around 40 years later. Similarly, it has been claimed that women who were exposed to the Chinese famine of 1959–1961 during pregnancy or early childhood are more likely to develop metabolic syndrome.

Recent studies have shown that even subtle imbalances in maternal nutrition are associated with the epigenetic profile at birth, which in turn is linked to markers of metabolic risk. Maternal carbohydrate consumption during the first trimester of pregnancy is inversely correlated with methylation levels at a single CpG in the RXRA gene in umbilical cord tissue and, in turn, is associated with child's adiposity at age 6 or 9 years of age. The early epidemiological data showed that the relation between birth weight and later disease risk is Ushaped; high birth weight also is associated with greater disease risk. This effect, although small in historical cohorts such as the Hertfordshire study, is very pronounced in populations such as the Pima who have a high prevalence of metabolic disease. There is now increasing epidemiological evidence that fetal over nutrition— as judged from indicators such as maternal obesity, excessive gestational weight gain, and gestational diabetes (GDM) – can produce a similar offspring phenotype to that of under-nutrition. For example, maternal body mass index (BMI) has been positively correlated with total and abdominal adiposity and with hepatic lipid content in infancy, across the entire range of maternal BMI. Exposure to a diabetic intrauterine milieu is a main risk factor for type 2 diabetes and is also associated with greater adiposity from infancy. Pregnancy weight gain that exceeds the medical guidelines is also associated with higher neonatal and early adult obesity. The epigenetic basis for these effects is now being explored.

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The dramatic increases in rates of overweight, obesity, and GDM in pregnant women during the past decade may have serious long-term consequences for public health. In many western countries, close to half of all expectant mothers are now overweight, and the prevalence of GDM in some Asian countries has increased to 20%. In Canadian First Nation populations, GDM may explain up to 30% of the highly increased incidence of type 2 diabetes in the next generation. These trends are generating a vicious trans-generational cycle of 'diabesity'.

3.8 Food Availability Links Mitochondrial Dysfunction and the Vicious Cycle of Oxidative Stress and Inflammation

The majority of non-communicable diseases, including cancer, atherosclerosis, Parkinson's disease, Alzheimer's disease, other neurodegenerative diseases, heart and lung abnormalities, diabetes, obesity, and autoimmune diseases, are caused by mitochondrial defects, systemic inflammation, and oxidative stress [10–16]. These problems are universally linked to obesity and its comorbidities, as well as to impairment of mitochondrial activity, which is necessary for optimal metabolism and health. There is ongoing discussion over the precise processes linking metabolic syndrome to obesity, aging, and mitochondrial dysfunction [17–22]. The liver, adipose tissue, skeletal muscles, pancreas, and hypothalamus are among the few vulnerable tissues where molecular messengers that control energy status also influence body weight [7, 23]. Important physical and molecular differences between humans and mice have been found in diet-induced obesity models, especially those pertaining to the development of fatty liver (NAFLD: nonalcoholic fatty liver disease) or nonalcoholic steatohepatitis (NASH) [24–30]. (Fig. 2). The conclusion that leptin is not a therapeutic option in humans deflated high expectations for a human cure following the creation of leptin-deficient mice (Ob/Ob) [28].

Efforts to store excess dietary energy immediately result in endoplasmic reticulum (ER) and mitochondrial stress, with the oxidative damage that follows [23, 29]. The homeostasis of glucose and lipid metabolism is maintained by adipokines derived from adipose tissue under normal weight conditions. However, in obese individuals, the dysregulated production of adipokines favors the development of metabolic syndrome and its associated complications, especially the accumulation of triglycerides in non-adipose organs that cause oxidative stress and inflammation [31]. The reasons behind this are unknown, as interventions to improve insulin resistance do not always result in a consistent clinical improvement [32]. To effectively manage non-communicable diseases, it is critical to comprehend the mechanisms that upset ER homeostasis, trigger the unfolded protein response, and result in mitochondrial abnormalities in metabolic diseases [33].

3.8.1) Link between Mitochondria and Nutrient Availability

Apoptosis is another basic process to consider in metabolic diseases. Excess food intake leads to mitochondrial dysfunction and higher apoptotic susceptibility. Mitochondria specialize in energy production and cell killing. Only 13 proteins are encoded by the mitochondrial DNA, a circular molecule of 16 Kb. The remaining necessary proteins are encoded in the nuclear DNA [86]. Mitochondria are composed of outer and inner specialized membranes that define two separate components, the matrix and the intermembrane space [87].

Mitochondria regulate apoptosis in response to cellular stress signals and determine whether cells live or die [88]. Thus, it is conceivable that the availability or ingestion of nutrients could be a main candidate in the regulation of cell death and that mitochondria could have been selected as a nutrient sensor and effector. This could explain the influence of apoptosis-related proteins on mitochondrial respiration [89].

As different studies shows excess food intake impairs respiratory capacities, likely through mTOR, and increases the susceptibility of the cell to apoptosis and additional stress [90, 91]. Of note, apoptotic protein levels are increased in the adipocytes of obese humans, and the depletion of proapoptotic proteins protects against liver steatosis and insulin resistance in mice fed a high-fat, high-cholesterol diet [92]. These conditions are relevant to the development of metabolic syndrome, as nutritional imbalances in Western diets lead to mitochondrial dysfunction and higher susceptibilities to inflammation, apoptosis, and aging [22].

3.9) Nutrition and lifespan

Nutrition, especially sensing and absorption of energy substances, not only plays an important role in the intensity of life activities and storage of energy substances but also controls aging and lifespan. More activity and rapid growth result in shorter life expectancy, and less activity and slower growth result in longer life expectancy. Members of SIRT protein family may play an important role in prolonging lifespan in nematodes. Although results of previous studies are controversial, physiological functions and mechanisms of these proteins have garnered interest [100]. Initially, Sir2 was recognized as an extra gene copy of non-expressible yeast mating type information gene [101]. Later, it was found that the Sir2 protein encoded by this gene has histone deacetylation activity that is dependent on NAD⁺ [102]. During the process of executing activity, in fact, NAD⁺ was degraded into nicotinamide and 1-O-acetyl-ADP-ribose [103]. Because NAD⁺/NADH serve as a cofactor in various metabolic reactions, Sir2 is speculated to perform a sensing role in cell metabolism [104]. This gene has seven homologous genes (SirT1–SirT7) in animals [105]. Proteins encoded by all these homologous genes contain a conserved domain that forms their catalytic core; however, all these proteins show different subcellular localization [106]. Metabolic pathway is considered to be a network. From a traditional view, the activities of enzymes involved in central metabolic pathways can be regulated, but the expression of these enzymes cannot be regulated.] However, many recent studies on various enzymes involved in the central metabolic pathway indicate that expression of these genes is regulated by posttranslational modification of nucleosome histones. Covalent modification of histones involves phosphorylation, acetylation, and methylation [107]. HATs [108] are special modifying enzymes that catalytically transfer active acetyl group from acetyl-CoA to amino group of lysine side chain in histones [109]. Molecules involved in nucleosome histone modifications, such as ATP, acetyl-CoA, and NAD⁺/NADH, are closely associated with energy metabolism. Thus, the modification status of histones after translation in the cytoplasm is an indicator of energy-supplying status of the body. Brian et al. [110] applied quantitative mass spectrometry to analyze acetylation kinetics and stoichiometric change in yeast. Their findings indicate an obvious difference in acetylation during growth and dormant periods and dependency on acetyl-CoA concentration. Concentration of acetyl-CoA in the mitochondria is significantly higher than that in the cytoplasm. These results suggest that histone acetylation reflects catabolism of glucose or fat and body's energy-supplying status through oxidative phosphorylation. Thus, more energy supply in the body can lead to higher accumulation of energy and exuberant energy metabolism, leading to a shorter lifespan. In contrast, energy restriction, appropriate starvation, or low calorie intake can reduce catabolism and oxidative phosphorylation, thus prolonging the lifespan. Its signaling pathways and logical relationships can be summarized as follows: High-energy nutrients (carbohydrates and fats) are digested and absorbed in the intestine. These nutrients are quantitatively sensed by GPCRs and then absorbed, stored, mobilized, and decomposed for energy supply by hormones secreted by the nerve and intestine–brain endocrine systems. More active catabolism and oxidative phosphorylation for energy supply result in shorter life expectancy and vice versa. Overall regulation of sugar catabolism depends on lactic acid cycle, and the overall regulation of fat catabolism depends on the circulation of ketone bodies.

4) Intervention mechanisms

4.1) Lifestyle intervention

NCDs are more likely to occur in those who are overweight or obese and who are less physically active [60]. In several populations, the emergence of NCD risk factors is linked to Western-style foods and a more sedentary lifestyle, which raises BMI. Consequently, weight-loss lifestyle changes aid to reduce NCD risk factors and consequences [61]. Additionally, prevention and quitting smoking are thought to be effective ways to avoid NCDs [24]. This technique has been successful in lowering morbidity and mortality in people with NCDs, in addition to the positive effects of lifestyle adjustment in preventing NCD risk factors and outcomes [8]. Losing $\geq 7\%$ of body weight with lifestyle adjustment appears to enhance insulin sensitivity and glycemic control in people with type 2 diabetes [63,64] and IGT [62], according to Trials (2009). A modest increase in activity helps maintain weight loss over the long run and enhances insulin sensitivity. Therefore, the American College

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of Sport and the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention recommend 150 minutes of moderate physical activity per week, such as walking. The World Health Organization does not view behavioral interventions as an appropriate means of preventing non-communicable diseases (NCDs), despite the fact that they have been shown to be feasible for preventing type 2 diabetes and certain other NCDs [66, 67]. Therefore, we excluded behavioral intervention from TLGS, with the exception of programs that assist individuals in managing stress.

4.2) Dietary intervention

Early preventative strategies should include exposing adults and children to palatable low-fat diets because increased dietary fat intake can contribute more calories than other macronutrients. Conversely, by reducing insulin levels, high-fiber diets may offer protection against obesity and CVDs [71, 72]. Multifaceted school-based treatments to lower the risk factors for obesity and non-communicable diseases were supported by some evidence [71–75].

5) Summary

In term of the relationship between foods and health, the following four key problems have to be addressed: (1) Undernutrition causes nutrition deficiency, and overnutrition leads to obesity, hypertension, hyperlipidemia, diabetes, and cancer. It also highlights that nutritional requirements of the body may vary among different individuals with different heredity and family backgrounds, different dietary habits, and living in different countries. Even different gut microbes may affect the requirement of nutrition. Diets determine the expression, regulation, modification, imprinting, and heredity of the genome without altering DNA sequences. Together with widely prevalent undernutrition, the epidemics of DR-NCDs, including obesity, hypertension, metabolic syndrome, T2DM, and CHD, are becoming a major public health challenge in glob.

In order to tackle the double burden of malnutrition, specific nutrition interventions and nutrition-sensitive development - with special emphasis on agriculture and trade policies - that take fully into account the need for preventing obesity and diet-related chronic diseases should be scaled up. Prevention of Low Birth Weight through better maternal nutrition, decreased exposure to environmental contaminants and antenatal care; increase of exclusive breastfeeding rates through the implementation of the Baby Friendly Hospital initiative, the Code of marketing breast milk substitutes and nutrition training of caregivers; improvement of complementary feeding through community programmes as well as better quality of commercial products are important actions that can benefit nutrition in the short term and contribute to NCD prevention in the longer term.

Healthy nutrition choices need to be accessible, affordable and safe for example by investing in diet diversification and sustainable small-scale agriculture. Improvements of availability and access to nutritious food need to be combined with correct utilization of it, which in turn depends on accurate knowledge of good nutrition and the social and cultural acceptability of a healthy diet; emphasis must be placed on family-level and village-level systems in which nutrition decisions are made. In addition utilization of most recommended lifestyle is very important in intervention of NCDs. In alignment with the WHO "Recommendations on the marketing of foods and non-alcoholic beverages to children", policies should be implemented in order to reduce the exposure of children to marketing messages that promote foods high in saturated fats, trans-fatty acids, free sugars, or salt, and to reduce the use of powerful techniques to market these foods to the societies.

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